

PROSPECTS FOR ENSURING ROAD SAFETY IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article provides scientific suggestions and practical recommendations on the basics of ensuring the safety of the state of the state of the state of law in the field of road industry, improving road infrastructure, improving the quality of roads, creating reliable conditions for the safe movement of vehicles and passengers in our country.

Keywords: Road, Traffic Safety, transport, pedestrians, car.

Introduction

In our country, in recent years, special attention has been paid to the development of the road industry, bringing roads to the level of international requirements. Modern road, roadbed, Bridge, pedestrian underground and surface roads are being built by road users, keeping the population's distance close and ensuring traffic safety.

On the organization of activities of the "Civil Aviation Agency under the Ministry of transport of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Inspectorate for supervision of the safety of freight and passenger transportation on railways and the Inspectorate for quality control of road and construction works" established by the decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 337 of April 19, 2021, the control over compliance with the requirements of urban planning legislation and regulatory documents related to the design, construction, reconstruction, repair and maintenance of highways and artificial structures by legal entities and individuals, as well as technical regulation in the field of production of road-building materials, objects and structures, participation in the work of commissions for the admission of completed road, it carries out a number of works on determining the quality indicators of road facilities based on the appeals of highway users.[1]

At the same time, in order to ensure Traffic Safety, special attention is paid to the presence of foci of traffic accidents, faults of the traffic part there, sidewalks, artificial lighting vehicles, road signs and road lines in the process of conducting quality control in road construction by the territorial departments of the Inspectorate for quality control of road and construction under the Ministry of transport.

Wide, flat and smooth roads, modern underground passages serve to reduce road traffic accidents, while making the passenger ring close, heavy, light, preventing excess time loss.

Traffic accidents decreased by 28.4 percent in 9 months of this year compared with the same period last year. Traffic accidents involving pedestrians decreased by 21.1%, in particular, 34.8% with children. Of course, this is the result of the reforms carried out in our country to bring roads to the level of international standards and ensure road safety. [2]

The huge creative work carried out in the road industry of our country is aimed at dramatically reducing the road-related expenses of drivers, making the passenger ring close,

especially ensuring safe movement, preventing the release of toxic gases into the atmosphere, and, consequently, preserving the purity of nature.

Literature review

A huge number of scientific studies are devoted to the problems of road safety. In a series of works devoted to traffic accident prevention, road safety problems, the high level of culture of the person driving the vehicle is cited as one of the main reasons. At the same time, the state of infrastructure in the country is also directly and indirectly influenced by the action security, which is covered by our local scientists in research work. In particular professor K. Azizov, I. Shukurov, J. Abdunazarov, M. Mikusova, J. Zhukovskaya, A. Usmanqulov, J. Sodikov and others have done a lot of research in the field of road safety.

J. In his article, Abdunazarov said: "the saturation of cities with cars, especially light cars, leads to excessive congestion of the urban street network, a decrease in traffic speed and a deterioration in road safety conditions. The transportation difficulties of historically developed large cities are complicated by the fact that they cannot go through large traffic flows. Large cities of the Republic of Uzbekistan are experiencing such difficulties that they should be ready to meet with a huge number of locally produced cars in the near future," he noted. [3]

Professor K. H. Azizov said in his research that 10-15 years ago, "the development of large cities in which the Republic of Uzbekistan chooses a model at the present stage of its development "will face a complex of transport problems characteristic of the city of Tashkent in the near future as a result of the rapid development of a number of cities of the Republic - Bukhara, Samarkand, Fergana, Andijan,". [4]

M. Duschanov believed that one of the most important of the operational indicators of highways is the fluidity of the coating. The fluidity of the coating is not only due to the ease of movement, motion safety, rather than the speed of motion, refers to the cost of transportation, i.e.

fuel consumption, cost of transportation, as well as roads and vehicles has also approached the term of service as having a significant effect.

According to the concept, Chuvikov "based on the mivar approach, which is dedicated to the study of the expert system of Accident Analysis. New models of Chuvikov reconstruction and examination will be discussed in his scientific work.

A. Ziakopolus has studied for decades the spatial analysis of accidents, how adjacent areas affect accidents in the field of road safety, how the effects of parameters in space change, and which areas require urgent intervention.

T. Carvey and T. Despite the most advanced modern active safety devices (up to SAE Level 2 Driving Automation), Tervo has now studied what fatal accidents can occur and how often these accidents occur.

Research methodology

The study made extensive use of existing scientific research on the regulation of road behavior, comparative comparison, statistical data editing and economic comparison and analysis, logical reasoning, scientific abstraction, information visualization, analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction methods.

Analysis and results

Since the appearance of the first car (1768 year.) with the development of Science and manufacturing, mass production of a movable vehicle has been established. To date, about

seventy million light cars are sold worldwide every year, and the total number of cars exceeds one million.

Unconditionally, the presence of a car creates comfort in our life and movement. But, the growth of the vehicle fleet also caused serious negative consequences. Since the first road accident in 1896, it has been known that one of the main problems in the use of a car is road accidents. [5]

According to the World Health Organization, 1.35 million people in the world per year are killed in a road traffic accident and more than 50 million people receive body injuries. An analysis of the Yths that have occurred in the last decades shows that about 10 thousand Yths have occurred in our Republic in one year, more than 2 thousand people are dying in them and about 11 thousand people are suffering bodily injuries. [6]

The population of Uzbekistan as of January 1, 2022. The number of vehicles was 36 million, and the number of vehicles was 3.6 million, with 1 car per 10. This suggests that most citizens are directly involved in the traffic process in the form of drivers, passengers and pedestrians. [7]

In order to ensure the safety of transport traffic and create favorable conditions for the population, existing domestic farm roads in our republic, roads that have become unusable in the villages are gradually reconstructed and converted into modern roads with stone-gravel, asphalt-concrete, cement-concrete and black coating. The decision of the president of the Republic of Azerbaijan on additional measures for the implementation of the programs "prosperous village" and "prosperous neighborhood" dated April 2, 2021, pq5048 serves as an important program in this regard.

This decision provides for further improvement of road infrastructure by bringing the state of road covers of highways to the required level, increasing the characteristics of their operation. With this, it is aimed at creating favorable conditions, especially in rural areas, as well as the promising development of sectors and territories of the economy of our country.

Discussion

The total length of highways in the Republic of Uzbekistan today is 209496 kilometers, based on the letters of the Cabinet of Ministers of Uzbekistan dated August 5, 2010 on approval of the list of highways in common use No. 169 and on additional measures for the implementation of the "Obod village "and" Obod mahalla "programs of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 2, 2021 on Of this, 42,869 is made up of nationwide highways and 141,882 is made up of inland farm highways and 24,745 is made up of departmental roads. The length of highways by region is shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Name of a territory	Total (km.)	Nationwide highways (km.)	Including (km.)			Domes tic farm roads (km.)	Depar tment al roads
			Interna tional import ance (km.)	State import ance (km.)	Local import ance (km.)		
Total Republic	209496	42869	3993	14203	24673	141882	24745

	Karakalpakstan	12388	4260	664	992	2604	8128	
	Andijan	13346	2463	103	800	1560	10883	
	Bukhara	15344	4012	540	1155	2317	11332	
	Djizzah	9354	2601	168	1431	1002	6753	
	Kashdarya	21677	3427	425	890	2172	18190	
	Navoi	9456	4017	302	2490	1225	5439	
	Namangan	14011	3377	111	1048	2218	10634	
	Samarkand	21903	4097	385	979	2733	17806	
0	Syrdarya	5214	1450	259	505	686	3764	
1	Surkhandaya	16170	2843	351	990	1502	13327	
6	Tashkent region	14219	4016	367	1241	2408	10203	
3	Fergana	19950	4031	193	873	2965	15919	
4	Kharezm	8939	2141	125	735	1281	6798	
5	Tashkent city.	2780	74	-	74	-	2706	
	Departmental roads	24745						

This year, a total of 21 trillion soums will be directed to work within the framework of these programs. It is also envisaged that 2 trillion soums will be allocated for the maintenance of more than 10 thousand kilometers of internal roads in 2,721 neighborhoods.

Conclusion.

It is necessary to carry out the following measures, taking measures to prevent our citizens from falling into unpleasant incidents during the traffic process:

I. In the direction of improving the regulatory framework in the field of ensuring road safety:

- * Strengthening the responsibility of road users for violations in the field of road safety;
- * Introduction of a modern scoring system that holds drivers accountable and encourages, taking into account the advanced foreign experience (PRC, Georgia, GFR, UK, France, Austria and other countries) [8];
- * Improvement and implementation of the legal mechanism for holding pedestrians accountable for traffic violations;
- * Improving procedures and grounds for parking vehicles on highways and holding special events;
- * Introduction of a regulatory mechanism for the use of modern information and communication technologies in the field of road safety, taking into account the "Safe City" project;

* To provide for additional measures to improve traffic rules and ensure road safety in it;

* Improvement of the procedure for mandatory technical inspection of vehicles;

II. In the direction of improving road infrastructure, improving the quality of roads, creating reliable conditions for the safe movement of vehicles and passengers:

* Providing access to safe, affordable, convenient and environmentally sustainable vehicles for all based on expanding access to public transport;

* Improvement of the infrastructure of international highways with the provision of optimal conditions for transit and transportation within the state;

* Provide for the improvement of the road network system of cities and settlements and the increase in the level of road safety in this. (installation of artificial lighting on all streets, curving of passages and above-ground pedestrian crossings, pedestal and bicycle lanes, adequate road signs, road lines and roadblocks and traffic lights;

- Identification of highway sections at high risk of road accidents and development of road infrastructure on those lands;

* Organization of immediate short-term emergency medical care for those injected in traffic accidents on Highway lots where traffic accidents occur a lot;

* Improvement of measures to prevent traffic accidents that occur by reducing the specific speed;

- To take measures to equip modern security systems (airbags, video recorders, loudspeakers when speed is brought, emergency medical notification devices when Yth accounts) with the introduction of information and communication technologies in the production process of cars;

* Improvement of measures aimed at preventing the accident of road accidents by a fault vehicle (implementation of measures to prohibit the use of cars that are excluded and have a service time, and hakozo);

* Introduction of intellectual Traffic Safety Systems (Automated road traffic control systems, a system of "smart" traffic lights that automatically control the flow of vehicles;

* Introduction of public-private partner mechanisms in the development of the road safety system;

III. In the direction of improving the legal culture and necessary qualifications of all participants in the road movement, strengthening their discipline:

* Reform of the training system for obtaining a driver's license;

- To take measures to reduce the human factor in the process of obtaining a driver's license;

* Adoption of comprehensive measures to prevent violations in the field of road safety;

* Wide involvement of public and civil society representatives in propaganda and propaganda measures on road safety;

- Introduction of qualitatively new mechanisms for attracting insurance companies to the promotion of traffic rules based on analysis of advanced foreign experience, as well as attracting operators of mobile communications and advertising companies to the promotion of road safety activities;

* Installation of means of promotion of road safety (advertising-information posters, shits • on public highways, where road traffic accidents are most common;

- Preparation of social rollers aimed at increasing the culture of compliance with traffic rules, as well as showing on the broadcasts of Republican and local TV channels;
- * The formation of knowledge, skills and skills in safe and law-abiding behavior in schoolchildren.

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